

Antioxidant and Hepatoprotective Activities of *Moringa oleifera* Leaves extracts in Albino Rats

Nabil, A. E. Azzaz¹, Hassan, B. Hamed², Sahar, E. Hamed¹ and Ahmed, M. Al Rifaie¹

¹Agricultural Chemistry Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Damietta University, Damietta, Egypt.

²Agricultural Chemistry Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt.

Abstract

Moringa oleifera is known by miracle tree. It has many advantages which make it used as medicinal herb in relieving many diseases. The antioxidant and hepatoprotective activities of *Moringa oleifera* leaves extracts were investigated against H₂O₂- induced hepatotoxicity in albino rats. Hepatotoxic rats were treated with methanolic and aqueous extracts of *Moringa oleifera* for a period of 45 days at the following two doses; 150 and 250 mg/kg body weight/day, orally. Aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), total bilirubin, total protein and albumin in Plasma, Gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (GGT) and catalase (CAT) were studied. The methanolic extract was the most effective against H₂O₂- induced hepatotoxicity. The treated hepatotoxicity rats showed upturn in all parameters. AST was decreased from 145 to 40 U/L, ALT from 154 to 37 U/L, ALP from 337 to 113 U/L, Alb was increased from 2.8 to 3.9 g/dl, Total protein from 4.8 to 6.28 g/dl, Gamma GT from 149 to 50 U/L and Total bilirubin from 1.97 to 0.78 mg/dl, and oxidative stress parameters. Catalase was increased from 1.94 to 3.04 U/. Results suggest that the antioxidant and hepatoprotective activities of *Moringa oleifera* leaves are possibly related to the free radical scavenging activity which might be due to the presence of total phenolics and flavonoids in the extract and the purified compounds Apigenin, P- hydroxy benzoic acid, Catechin and rutin which were found in methanolic extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaves.

Keywords: antioxidants, free radicals, hepatoprotection, *Moringa oleifera*, methanolic, aqueous.

Introduction

Medicinal plants spread all over the world. These plants including the moringa tree, called the miracle tree, which belongs to *Moringaceae* and used for medical purposes. It is native to the sub-Himalayan tracts of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh,

Afghanistan, ancient Romans, Greeks and Egyptians (Fahey 2005). *Moringa oleifera* leaves are rich of macro- and micronutrients including polyphenols, phenolic acids, vitamins, carotenoids, flavonoids, and alkaloids. Maizuwo *et al.*, (2017). *Moringa oleifera* seeds contain α , γ and δ -

Tocopherols, β sitosterol, campestral, and Δ^5 , avenasterol. **Farooq and Rashid (2007)**. gallic acid, chlorogenic acid, ellagic acid, ferulic acid, kaempferol, quercetin and vanillin are the main components of flavonoids of moringa oleifera leaves **Valdez-Solana et al., (2015)**. Hepatoprotective activity Cirrhosis is the destruction of hepatocytes and following substitution with 'scar tissue' which alter the flow of blood through liver leading to the death of hepatocytes and n function of the liver (**Wang and Nagrath, 2011**). The event of liver damage is followed by 'hepatic fibrosis' whereby regeneration of apoptotic cells is observed after 'repeated injury' (**Friedman et al., 2002**) In the event, when the death of regenerating cells occurs, deposition of extracellular matrix is observed, which leads to deposition of 'fibrillar collagen' (**O'Connell and Rushworth, 2008**). Such pathology is difficult to treat. The effectiveness of treatment with colchicine's, interferons, penicillamine and corticosteroids are contradictory and seem to be questionable. As oxidative stress is one of the causes beneath cirrhosis, use of antioxidants could be a unique strategy for treatment. Different parts of moringa act as anti-hepatotoxic activity (**Ruckmani et al., 1998**) cardiac and

circulatory stimulants, **Anwar et al., (2007)** possess antitumor, antipyretic, **Farooq et al., (2012)** antiepileptic, anti-inflammatory, **Mishra, et al., (2012)** antiulcer, antispasmodic, diuretic, (**Basit et al., 2015**) antihypertensive, cholesterol lowering, **Gopalakrishnan et al., (2016)** antioxidant, antidiuretic, hepatoprotective, antibacterial and antifungal activities. **Karim et al., (2016)**.

Materials and methods

Plant collection and identification: Leaves of Egyptian *moringa oleifera* were collected from Faculty of Agriculture, Damietta University, Egypt in February 2017. The leaves of plant were identified by botanical members of the Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University. The leaves were allowed to dry in a shady and well-aired place, then dried at 50°C and grounded into a powder using commercial blender and finally used for analysis.

Extraction with water (aqueous extract): 500gm powder of moringa dry leaves was macerated in 1.5 L of distilled water for 24 h. at room temperature .the water extracts was filtered through what man (No.1) filter paper .the process was repeated 3 times .the filtrates were combined and dried using rotary evaporator under vaccum.the dried extract was kept at 4°C till use .The

extraction procedure was carried out according to **Wilson et al ., (1997)**.

Extraction with Methanol (methanolic extract) : 500gm powder of moringa dry leaves was macerated in 1.5 L of methanol 70 %for 24 h.at room temperature .the methanol extracts was filtered through what man (No.1) filter paper .the process was repeated 3 times .the filtrates were combined and dried using rotary evaporator under vaccum.the dried extract was kept at 4°C till use The extraction technique was carried out according to (**Rampadarath et al., 2014**).

Experimental animals: Adult male albino rats (150 ± 10 g) were obtained from the Memorial Institute of Ophthalmology in Giza Egypt. All the animals were kept in plastic cages and placed in a well-ventilated rat house (temperature was 22 ± 2 °C and lighting condition were natural light from large windows during the day and complete darkness during the night), and were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for 2 weeks prior to start the experiment. Rats were kept on a balanced diet throughout the experimental period.

Quantitative identification of phenolics and flavonoids by HPLC: Flavonoids and

polyphenolics was Quantitative A modified method of **Zuo, et al., (2002)**

Experimental design:

Randomized groups of rats were divided to 6 groups, each group consist of 10 male rats.

Group1: Rats kept without any treatments as control fed on standard diet, named normal control or negative control (healthy group) (I).

Group 2- Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water, named positive control or diseased group (II).

Group 3- Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water only for 15 days , then watery extract of *moringa leaves* at orally dose of 150 mg/kg bw (III).

Group 4- Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water only for 15 days, then watery extract of *moringa leaves* at orally dose of 250 mg/kg bw (IV).

Group 5- Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water only for 15 days, then methanolic extract of *moringa leaves* at orally dose of 150 mg/kg bw (V).

Group 6- Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water only for 15 days, then methanolic extract of *moringa leaves* at orally dose of 250 mg/kg bw (VI).

- Plant extract were given daily by stomach tube and the blood samples were taken at 0,

15, 30 and 45 days of the experimental period for biochemical analysis.

Preparation of blood samples: Blood samples were collected from orbital sinus veins using heparinized capillary tubes at the end of experimental period, into clean, dry, and labeled Eppendorf tubes (1.5 ml). The tubes contained heparin as anticoagulant (7.5 I. U/ml blood) according to **Schalm (1986)**.

Determination of aspartate transaminase AST activity: The activity of aspartate aminotransferase was determined by enzymatic colorimetric method in plasma as described by **Young, (1990)**.

Determination of alanine transaminase ALT activity: The activity of alanine aminotransferase was determined by enzymatic colorimetric method in plasma as described by **Young, (1990)**.

Determination of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity: Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) was determined colorimetrically in plasma as described by **Moss, et al, (1987)**.

Determination of Gamma-Glutamyl transferase: Gamma Glutamyl transferase was determined in plasma as described by **(Saw et al., 1983)**.

Determination of Total protein: Total protein was determined in plasma as described by **(Schultze and Heremans, 1966)**.

Determination of Total Bilirubin: Bilirubin Total was determined in plasma as described by **(Tietz 1990)**.

Determination of catalase (CAT) activity: Catalase activity was determined in plasma as described by **(Aebi 1984)**.

Results

It was clear that, H₂O₂ treatment increased AST and ALT significantly from 22 and 24 at zero-time and reached 154 and 164 U/L after 45 days, respectively. Such an increase may be due damage in liver tissues. Data in table (2) showed that the most effect was observed by treatment with methanol extract 250 mg/kg b.w. which decreased AST and ALT parameters from 154 and 164 to 40 and 37 U/L after 45 days, respectively.

Table (3) show the ALP parameter for both controls and experimental treated groups after zero, 15, 30, 45 days. It can be observed that ALP parameter is significantly increased in positive control comparing with negative control. The most effect was observed by treatment with methanol extract 250 mg/kg bw where ALP parameter decreased from 337 to 113U/L after 45 days.

Also, it can be observed that the Alb parameter is significantly decreased in positive control comparing with negative control. The most effect was observed by the treatment with methanol extract 250 mg/kg bw which increased ALb parameter from 2.8 to 3.9 g/dl after 45 days.

From table (4), it can be observed that total protein (TP) parameter is significantly decreased in positive control comparing with negative control from 6.4 and which reached 4.8 g/dl after 45 days. The most effect was observed by treatment with methanol extract 250 mg/kg bw increased TP parameter from 4.8 to 6.28g/dl after 45

days. GGT parameter decreased from 149 to 50U/L after 45 days by treatment with methanol extract 250 mg/kg bw.

Table (5) shows that at zero-time H₂O₂ treatment increased total bilirubin significantly from 0.47 which reached 1.97 mg/dl after 45 days. Methanolic extract 250 mg/kg bw decreased total bilirubin from 1.92 to 0.78 mg/dl after 45 days. H₂O₂ treatment decreased CAT parameter significantly from 3.11 which reached 1.94 U/L after 45 days. CAT parameter is increased from 1.94 to 3.04 U/L after 45 days by treatment with methanol extract 250 mg/kg bw.

Table (1): HPLC analysis of flavonoid and phenolic components of moringa leaves.

Compound	Conc(ug/g)
Gallic acid	22.827
Protocatechuic	15.662
<i>p</i> -hydroxybenzoic acid	204.830
Gentisic acid	1.813
Catechin	203.796
Chlorogenic acid	37.001
Caffeic acid	184.626
Syringic acid	29.415
Vanillic acid	67.371
Scopoletin	ND
Ferulic acid	52.936
Sinapic acid	9.139
<i>p</i> -coumaric acid	ND
Rutin	814.412
Naringinin	ND
Apigenin-7-glucoside	608.606
Rosmarinic acid	31.498
Cinnamic acid	ND
Lutiolin	7.919
Apigenin	ND
Kaempferol	ND
Chrysin	ND

Table (2) Effect of moringa leaves extracts on liver function (AST) and (ALT) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats.

Name and unit Days/ Treatment	AST (U/L)				ALT (U/L)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative	22	22	23	22	24	23	24	24
Positive	22	81	107	154	23	81	109	164
Group 1	23	83	64	53	24	77	57	48
Group 2	22	84	53	40	23	79	53	37
Group 3	22	78	65	56	23	82	66	51
Group 4	23	84	68	42	23	85	59	40

Table (3) Effect of moringa leaves extracts on liver function (ALP) and (ALb) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats.

Name and unit Days Treatment	ALP (U/L)				ALb (g/dL)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative 1	90	90	90	91	4.1	4.1	4.11	4.1
Positive 2	92	179	288	337	4.1	3.66	3.27	2.8
Group 3	92	173	158	142	4.1	3.61	3.68	3.81
Group 4	91	168	151	113	4.11	3.52	3.77	3.9
Group 5	90	177	167	144	4.1	3.64	3.67	3.77
Group 6	90	171	159	136	4.09	3.49	3.75	3.86

Table (4) Effect of moringa leaves extracts on liver function (TP) and (GGT) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats.

Name and unit Days Treatment	TP (g/dL)				GGT (U/L)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative 1	6.4	6.4	6.42	6.4	23	23	23	24
Positive 2	6.4	6.1	5.4	4.8	23	81	109	149
Group 3	6.32	6.08	6.13	6.19	24	85	73	67
Group 4	6.37	6.11	6.2	6.28	24	84	59	50
Group 5	6.38	6.03	6.12	6.17	23	82	77	66
Group 6	6.4	6.02	6.14	6.22	23	85	65	57

Table (5) Effect of moringa leaves extracts on liver function (Bili Total) oxidative stress (CAT) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats.

Name and unit Days Treatment	T. Bili (mg/dL)				CAT (U/L)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative 1	0.47	0.45	0.45	0.46	3.11	3.12	3.11	3.11
Positive 2	0.46	1.12	1.45	1.97	3.11	2.73	2.26	1.94
Group 3	0.46	1.14	0.98	0.92	3.11	2.68	2.87	2.93
Group 4	0.45	1.1	0.84	0.78	3.12	2.71	2.90	3.04
Group 5	0.47	1.15	1.0	0.95	3.12	2.69	2.84	2.91
Group 6	0.48	1.17	0.9	0.83	3.11	2.77	2.94	3.01

Discussion

The majority of the experiments confirmed the benefits of *moringa oleifera* and its role in protection liver. Phenolics and flavonoids are active antioxidant components in the leaves of *M. oleifera* Verma *et al* (2009). The major compounds were isolated and identified as *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, Catechin, Rutin, Apigenin-7-glucoside and Caffeic acid, which expressed exceptionally strong antioxidant activity in many studies (Jung *et al* 2010). Plant phenolic compounds are secondary plant metabolites and are involved in the normal growth, development, acting as defense mechanisms of plants against pathogenic, parasites infection and free radicals' generation (Maisuthisakul, *et al.*, 2007). The present study revealed higher values of phenols, flavonoids, flavonols and proanthocyanidins in methanolic extract of *M. oleifera* leaves than the aqueous extract. The observed results could be due to different degree of polarity of the solvents used for the extraction of polyphenolic compounds and thus could contribute significantly to the antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity. The phenolic content of *M. oleifera* leaves observed in this study corroborated with the findings of Atawodi, *et al.*, (2010) on different fractions

of this plant. The synergistic effect of phenolic compounds may contribute significantly to the ability of the extracts to adsorb and neutralize free radicals or decompose peroxides (Adedapo, *et al.*,2008). Their ability as free radical scavengers could be due to their redox properties, presence of conjugated ring structures and carboxylic group which have been reported to inhibit lipid peroxidation (Oyedemi, *et al.*, 2010). Our findings could be attributed to the high phenolic contents especially flavonoids in the methanolic extract. The flavonoids and phenolic active compounds in this *plant can* act as hepatoprotective agents because of their antioxidant and scavenging properties and protect rats against H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress in liver. This theory was confirmed by the detected lipid peroxidation in this study. Moreover, the maximum protective effect of methanolic extract was observed in H₂O₂-treated rats administered with 100 mg/kg body weight of extract. (Zhang, *et al.*, (2011; Leone, *et al.*, 2015). Apigenin induces cell cycle arrest at different proliferation stages (Kashyap, *et al.*, 2018). Also promotes different anti-inflammatory pathways (Huang, *et al.*, 2010). (McKay and Blumberg, 2002) who revealed that physiological responses to catechin may be

relevant to the promotion of health, as well as the prevention or treatment of these chronic diseases. (Nemec, *et al.*, 2016) reported that gallic acid can exert its cytotoxic and antitumor effect via modulation of antioxidant/pro-oxidant balance. In some cases, the compound can control the reactive oxygen species (ROS)-induced carcinogenesis through increasing the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione reductase (GR), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and/or by reducing the lipid peroxidation and ROS production. (Jagan, *et al.*, 2008) showed that in the case of hepatocellular carcinoma, gallic acid decreased the tumor size and the serum level of tumor marker enzymes such as aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) by inhibiting the proliferation of hepatic cells. Rutin is extensively studied for hepatoprotective activity in experimental animals. (Khan *et al.*, 2012a, Khan *et al.*, 2012b) evaluated the protective effect of rutin in carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced liver injuries in rats. Administration of rutin caused a decrement in levels of alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase and

gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase in serum raised due to carbon tetrachloride. The level of cholesterol in blood was regulated whereas the level of endogenous liver antioxidant enzymes such as catalase, superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione-S-transferase, glutathione reductase and glutathione was increased, whereas lipid peroxidation was decreased in a dose-dependent manner. Along with this, the activity of p53 and CYP2E1 was restored by treatment with rutin. In an independent study in BALB/c mice, rutin treatment allayed oxaliplatin-induced hepatotoxicity and neurotoxicity. Prevention of mechanical allodynia along with histopathological observations suggested the protective role of rutin in the prevention of hepatotoxicity (Schwingel *et al.*, 2014). Rats which were exposed to H₂O₂ exhibited histo-pathological alterations including cytoplasm vacuolization, congestion, infiltration, and degeneration of hepatocytes (necrosis). Rahim *et al.*, (2014). In this study Aspartate aminotransferase, alanine aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase and gamma glutamyl transferase enzymes activities as well as total bilirubin in plasma increased in H₂O₂-treated rats (positive control) compared with that in the control rats (negative control)

Furthermore, the Alb, Tp, CAT of H₂O₂-treated rats (positive control) were markedly reduced compared with that in group 1(negative control) *M. oleifera* methanolic extract of 250 /100 mg·kg⁻¹ body weight give a best results and decreased the levels of the parameters relative to that of the H₂O₂-treated rats (positive control) and increased Alb, Tp, CAT these results due to the presence of total phenolics and flavonoids in the extract and the purified compounds Apigenin, P-hydroxy benzoic acid, Catechin rutin, quercetin and kaempferol, which were found in methanolic extract of *Moringa oleifera* leaves. The activities of the liver function enzymes, as well as Tp, TB concentrations and histological changes are good biomarkers for liver injury and evaluating the protective effect of medicinal plants (Xie *et al.*, 2012). The present study demonstrates that *moringa oleifera* leaves extracts attenuates liver damage due to H₂O₂ administration as indicated by the significant reduction in the elevated levels of ALT, AST, ALP, GGT, Total bilirubin in plasma increase in Tp, Alb, CAT in plasma and improvement of histological changes

Conclusion: Taken together, study suggests that *Moringa oleifera* has Hepatoprotective and antioxidant Activities due to total

phenolics and flavonoids, these components has many benefits for the oxidative stress by improving liver function

Reference

- Adedapo, A. A.; Jimoh, F. O.; Afolayan, A. J. and Masika, P. J. (2008).** Antibacterial and antioxidant properties *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 8, 53.of the methanol extracts of the leaves and stems of *Calpurnia aurea*.
- Aebi, H. (1984).** [13] Catalase in vitro. *In Methods in enzymology* (Vol. 105, pp. 121-126). Academic Press.
- Anwar, F.; Latif, S.; Ashraf, M. and Gilani, A. H. (2007).** *Moringa oleifera*: a food plant with multiple medicinal uses. *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*, 21(1), 17-25.
- Atawodi, S. E.; Atawodi, J. C.; Idakwo, G. A., Pfundstein, B.; Haubner, R.; Wurtele, G. and Owen, R. W. (2010).** Evaluation of the polyphenol content and antioxidant properties of methanol extracts of the leaves, stem, and root barks of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. *Journal of Medicinal Food*, 13(3), 710-716.

Basit, A.; Rizvi, A.; Badruddeen, A. J.; and Mishra, A. (2015). Phytochemical and Pharmacological Overview of Sahajan (*Moringa oleifera*). *Int. J. Pharma Chemical Research, 1(4)*, 156-164.

Fahey, J. W. (2005). *Moringa oleifera*: a review of the medical evidence for its nutritional, therapeutic, and prophylactic properties. Part 1. *Trees for life Journal, 1(5)*, 1-15.

Farooq, A. and U. Rashid. (2007). Physicochemical characteristics of *Moringa oleifera* seeds and seed oil from a wild provenance of Pakistan. *Pak. J. Bot., 39(5)*: 1443- 1453,

Farooq, F.; Rai, M.; Tiwari, A.; Khan, A. A. and Farooq, S. (2012). Medicinal properties of *Moringa oleifera*: An overview of promising healer. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research, 6(27)*, 4368-4374.

Friedman, A.; Kerkman, D. D. and Brown, N. R. (2002). Spatial location judgments: A cross-national comparison of estimation bias in subjective North American geography. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review, 9(3)*, 615-623.

Gopalakrishnan, L.; Doriya, K. and Kumar, D. S. (2016). *Moringa oleifera*: A review on nutritive importance and its medicinal application. *Food science and human wellness, 5(2)*, 49-56.

Huang, C. H.; Kuo, P. L.; Hsu, Y. L.; Chang, T. T.; Tseng, H. I.; Chu, Y. T. and Hung, C. H. (2010). The natural flavonoid apigenin suppresses Th1-and Th2-related chemokine production by human monocyte THP-1 cells through mitogen-activated protein kinase pathways. *Journal of medicinal food, 13(2)*, 391-398.

Jagan, S.; Ramakrishnan, G.; Anandakumar, P.; Kamaraj, S. and Devaki, T. (2008). Antiproliferative potential of gallic acid against diethyl nitrosamine-induced rat hepatocellular carcinoma. *Molecular and cellular biochemistry, 319(1-2)*, 51.

Jung, S. H.; Kim, B. J.; Lee, E. H. and Osborne, N. N. (2010). Isoquercetin is the most effective antioxidant in the plant *Thuja orientalis* and able to counteract oxidative-induced damage to a transformed cell line (RGC-5 cells). *Neurochemistry international, 57(7)*, 713-721.

Karim, N. A. A.; Ibrahim, M. D.; Kntayya, S. B.; Rukayadi, Y.;Hamid, H. A.; and Razis, A. F. A. (2016). *Moringa oleifera* Lam: targeting chemoprevention. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev, 17*, 3675-3686.

Kashyap, D.; Sharma, A.; Tuli, H. S.; Sak, K.; Garg, V. K.; Buttar, H. S. and Sethi, G. (2018). Apigenin: A natural bioactive flavone-type molecule with

promising therapeutic function. *Journal of functional foods*, 48, 457-471.

Khan, R. A.; Khan, M. R. and Sahreen, S. (2012). CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity: protective effect of rutin on p53, CYP2E1 and the antioxidative status in rat. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine*, 12(1), 178.

Khan, R. A.; Khan, M. R. and Sahreen, S. (2012). Protective effects of rutin against potassium bromate induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine*, 12(1), 204.

Leone, A.; Spada, A.; Battezzati, A.; Schiraldi, A., Aristil, J. and Bertoli, S. (2015). Cultivation, genetic, ethno pharmacology, photochemistry and pharmacology of *Moringa oleifera* leaves: an overview. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 16(6), 12791-12835.

Maisuthisakul, P.; Suttajit, M. and Pongsawatmanit, R. (2007). Assessment of phenolic content and free radical-scavenging capacity of some Thai indigenous plants. *Food chemistry*, 100(4), 1409-1418.

Maizuwo, A. I.; Hassan, A. S.; Momoh, H. and Muhammad, J. A. (2017). Phytochemical constituents, biological activities, therapeutic potentials and nutritional values of *Moringa oleifera*

(Zogale): a review. *Journal of drug design and medicinal chemistry*, 3(4), 60.

McKay, D. L. and Blumberg, J. B. (2002). The role of tea in human health: an update. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 21(1), 1-13.

Mishra, S. P.; Singh, P., and Singh, S. (2012). Processing of *Moringa oleifera* leaves for human consumption. *Bulletin of Environment, Pharmacology and life sciences*, 2(1), 28-31.

Moss, D. W.; Henderson, A. R. and Kachmar, J. F. (1987). Enzymes in: Tietz NW, ed. *Fundamentals of clinical chemistry*.

Nemec, M. J.; Kim, H.; Marciante, A. B.; Barnes, R. C.; Talcott, S. T. and Mertens-Talcott, S. U. (2016). Pyrogallol, an absorbable microbial gallotannins-metabolite and mango polyphenols (*Mangifera Indica* L.) suppress breast cancer ductal carcinoma in situ proliferation in vitro. *Food & function*, 7(9), 3825-3833.

O'Connell, M. A. and Rushworth, S. A. (2008). Curcumin: potential for hepatic fibrosis therapy?. *British journal of pharmacology*, 153(3), 403-405.

Oyedemi, S. O., Bradley, G. and Afolayan, A. J. (2010). In-vitro and-vivo antioxidant activities of aqueous extract of *Strychnos henningsii* Gilg. *African Journal*

of pharmacy and pharmacology, 4(2), 070-078.

Rahim, S. M.; Taha, E. M.; Al-janabi, M. S.; Al-douri, B. I.; Simon, K. D. and Mazlan, A. G. (2014). Hepatoprotective effect of *Cymbopogon citratus* aqueous extract against hydrogen peroxide-induced liver injury in male rats. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 11(2), 447-451.

Rampadarath, S.; Puchooa, D. and Ranghoo-Sanmukhiya, M. (2014). Antimicrobial, phytochemical and insecticidal properties of *Jatropha* species and wild *Ricinus communis* L. found in Mauritius. *Int J Pharm Phytochem Res*, 6, 831-840.

Ruckmani, K.; Kavimani, S.; An, R. and Jaykar, B. (1998). Effect of *Moringa oleifera* Lam on paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 60(1), 33.

Saw, M.; Stromme, J. H.; Iondon, J. L. and Theodorsen, L. (1983). IFCC method for g-glutamyle transferase (g-glutamyl)-peptide: amino acid g-glutamyle transferase. *Clin. Chem. Acta*, 135, 315F-338F.

Schalm, O.W. (1986). Veterinary Haematology. 4th ed., Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, pp.21-86.

Schultze, H. E. and Heremans, J. F. (1966). Molecular biology of human proteins with special reference to plasma proteins. Vol. 1. Nature and metabolism of extracellular proteins. *Molecular biology of human proteins with special reference to plasma proteins*. Vol. 1. *Nature and metabolism of extracellular proteins*.

Schwingel, T. E.; Klein, C. P.; Nicoletti, N. F.; Dora, C. L.; Hadrich, G.; Bica, C. G. and Morrone, F. B. (2014). Effects of the compounds resveratrol, rutin, quercetin, and quercetin nanoemulsion on oxaliplatin-induced hepatotoxicity and neurotoxicity in mice. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's archives of pharmacology*, 387(9), 837-848.

Tietz, N. W. (1990). Clinical Guide to Laboratory Tests 2nd Ed. Philadelphia. Tovar D, Zambonino-Infante JL, Cahu C, Gatesoupe FJ, Vázquez-Juárez R, Lésel R (2002). Effect of live yeast incorporation in compound diet on digestive enzyme activity in sea bass larvae. *Aquaculture*, 204, 113-123.

Valdez-Solana, M. A.; Mejía-García, V. Y.; Téllez-Valencia, A.; García-Arenas, G.; Salas-Pacheco, J.; Alba-Romero, J. J. and Sierra-Campos, E. (2015). nutritional content and elemental and phytochemical analyses of *Moringa oleifera*

grown in Mexico. *Journal of Chemistry*, 2015.

Verma, A. R.; Vijayakumar, M.;

Mathela, C. S. and Rao, C. V. (2009). In vitro and in vivo antioxidant properties of different fractions of *Moringa oleifera* leaves. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 47(9), 2196-2201.

Wang, S. and Nagrath, D. (2011). Liver tissue engineering. In *Biomaterials for Tissue Engineering Applications* (pp. 389-419). Springer, Vienna.

Wilson, P. G.; Zheng, Y.; Oakley, C. E.; Oakley, B. R.; Borisy, G. G. and Fuller, M. T. (1997). Differential expression of two γ -tubulin isoforms during gametogenesis and development in *Drosophila*. *Developmental biology*, 184(2), 207-221.

Xie, Q.; Guo, F. F. and Zhou, W. (2012). Protective effects of cassia seed ethanol extract against carbon tetrachloride-induced liver injury in mice. *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, 59(2).

Young, D.S. (1990). Effects of drugs on clinical laboratory tests. Third edition 4th Ed. Washington, DC; *AACC Press*: 3:6 -12.

Zhang, M.; Hettiarachchy, N. S.; Horax, R.; Kannan, A.; Praisoody, A. and Muhundan, A. (2011). Phytochemicals, antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, *Centella asiatica*,

Moringa oleifera and *Murraya koenigii* leaves. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 5(30), 6672-6680.

Zuo, Y.; Chen, H. and Deng Y. (2002). Simultaneous determination of catechins, caffeine and gallic acids in green, Oolong, black and pu-erh teas using HPLC with a photodiode array detector. *Talanta*, 57(2), 307-316.